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**Classificazione delle galassie usando il machine
learning**

(Classification of galaxies using machine learning)

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Abstract

In this work, I investigate the possibility of finding a data-driven solution to the problem of automatic classification of galaxies using machine learning methods. In the modern scientific contest, the ability to reliably classify distant galaxies is important not only because it allows us to better understand their formation and evolution, but also because it possibly enables us to gain a better insight into the structure formation of our Universe. Due to the lack of a reliable knowledge base and also to minimize human biases, I tested two unsupervised methods on spectra obtained from the Data Release 3 of the Galaxy And Mass Assembly survey (GAMA): namely an Unsupervised Random Forest (URF) and a combination of T-distributed Stochastic Neighbor Embedding (T-SNE) and Density-Based Spatial Clustering of Applications with Noise (DBSCAN). Both algorithms have often been used and validated in various astrophysical contexts but while URF has been successfully used on both star and galaxy spectra (for example *Reis et al. 2018*^[62] and *Baron et al. 2017*^[9]), T-SNE, to my knowledge, has been only used on spectra of stars (*Traven et al. 2017*)^[84].

A sample of approximately 72,000 good quality spectra has been selected from the original set of 166,000 ones available from the GAMA DR3. Each spectrum has been normalized by fitting and subtracting its continuum, then it has been de-redshifted to the rest frame and, finally, it has been rebinned and trimmed to get a set of fluxes in 2250 different wavelength bins ranging from 3700Å to 7000Å. This range has been chosen to minimize the number of noisy pixels and missing data. The whole sample of spectra has been imputed to fill any missing data.

The reduced sample of spectra has been analyzed with URF first, from which however no conclusive result can be extrapolated.

In a second experiment, I tried to perform a clustering process with DBSCAN on the sample. However, due to its high dimensionality, no clustering algorithm can be successfully used directly on the dataset of spectra, and a dimensionality reduction phase with T-SNE is needed beforehand, in which I tested several metrics. Only two of them produced a valid result in a reasonable amount of time: the so-called ‘hamming’ metric and the ‘correlation’ metric. After this dimensionality reduction phase, I run DBSCAN on the reduced dataset to search possible clusters.

Using the ‘correlation’ metric, I was able to identify one main cluster surrounded by a small set of noise points, which are spectra dissimilar from every other one in the sample. I then applied DBSCAN recursively on the main central cluster, finding a total of 27 clusters organized hierarchically. The objects in each cluster appear to have very similar spectral features, total stellar masses, age, and other physical properties. From these clusters I also derived a set of 27 spectral templates that could be used to estimate the type of objects and its redshift using cross-correlation techniques.

Chapter 1

Introduction

1.1 History of galaxies classification

Despite the fascination that extended objects in the sky exerted on astronomers, the concept of the galaxy, as we know it today, was introduced very recently. It was Edwin Hubble in the early 1920s who provided a definitive answer. Thanks to the use of the Hooker telescope located on Mount Wilson, the scientist was able to resolve the external parts of some nebulae by defining them as a set of stars and establishing that they were at excessive distances to belong to the Milky Way. Galaxies were finally defined as such and their study and cataloging started.

Hubble developed the classification sequence (Fig. 1.1) by observing very bright and easily resolvable galaxies, usually giants and supergiants that are found isolated or in small clusters. His considerations regarding the morphological structure of the objects he had studied led him to conclude that the sequence he described represented a temporal succession, that is, an evolution of such systems from the Early-Type region to the Late-Type region. The link between the two categories was identified in the structure of the S0, or *Lenticular* galaxies that share proper-

Figure 1.1: Hubble diagram: on the left there are the Early-type galaxies, on the right the Late-type. (CC BY-SA 3.0)

ties in common to both. Today it is known that the evolution model is incorrect, although Hubble's classification is still used alongside his terminology.

According to the Hubble taxonomy, galaxies were organized into the following classes:

Early-type: characterized by a regular profile and without important substructures. These systems are often considered “old” due to the stellar population that compose them (prevalence of brown and red dwarfs) and which highlights the lack of formation of new stars. They are also characterized by the presence of gas in the hot phases and by the absence of dust. The surface brightness is greater in the center and gradually decreases as you move towards the edge, until it merges with the background of the intergalactic sky. *Elliptical* and *Lenticular* galaxies are generally considered early-type. The *Elliptical* galaxies are distributed in the Universe with very varied shapes and sizes, whose masses can alternate from billions of solar masses (for example the giants observed by Hubble), to the few millions that distinguish the weak dwarf galaxies. The presence of *Elliptical* galaxies is a function of the local density of galaxies, and they can vary from 10% in the less populated regions up to 40% in the centers of the densest clusters. *Lenticular* galaxies are placed in the middle of the Hubble diagram, having characteristics in common with elliptical and spiral galaxies. They are characterized by central regions that are brighter than the external components which instead follow a brightness distribution more similar to spiral galaxies and which may present dust. They have no obvious structures, apart from the swelling of the central bulge with respect to the surrounding flat disk (similar to that of the spirals, but without arms), a phenomenon that gives the recognizable “lens” shape. They are generally identified with $S0n$ and are divided into:

- i) normal lenticulars, divided into $S01$, $S02$ and $S03$, according to the degree of absorption of dust in the disc.
- i) barred lenticulars, classified in $SB01$, $SB02$, $SB03$.

where this time the subdivision depends on the prominence of the bar (due to the differential motion of rotation).

Late-type: they develop in the Hubble diagram after the lenticular galaxies. Their integrated color is classically blue, which indicates the presence of a stellar population younger than the *Elliptical* ones (and the $S0$) and of star formation still in progress. The morphology of these systems is decidedly more complicated and intriguing due to the presence of regions rich in cold gas

and dust. They are divided into *Spiral* and *Irregular* galaxies. The former constitute the most representative category of the late-type group and are by far the most famous and striking galaxies. In the Universe, they are mainly found in low-density regions while they are almost completely absent in the central regions of the clusters. They are formed by a rotating disk characterized by an angular momentum even five times higher than that of elliptical galaxies. Its composition is made up of agglomerates of cold gases, dust, open clusters and young, very hot stars that give the integrated spectrum the blue color. The classification of the spirals is divided according to the shape of the bulge: *S* if the bulge has spherical symmetry, *Sb* if it has an elongated structure. In this case it is called “*barred*”, and the spiral arms are emanated from the ends of the bar. Furthermore, both classes of *Spirals* are divided in turn into three types: *a*, *b*, *c*. In particular, the criteria used for the distinction are the following

- i) the size and brightness of the bulge with respect to the one of the disc;
- ii) the degree of winding of the arms;
- iii) the resolving capacity of the spirals in the individual stars and emitting nebulae (HII regions)

So there are *Sa* and *SBa* galaxies (early-type spirals) with a very large bulge and with little gas. The arms are quite wrapped, generally well defined, but not very solvable. On the opposite side, the galaxies of category *Sc* and *SBc* (late-type spirals) may also have almost no trace of the bulge and have very open and well-resolved arms. The middle stages are designated by categories *Sb* and *SBb*. Irregular galaxies are purely asymmetrical galaxies and generally of low mass. They are widespread in the Universe, but they glow with rather dim light. They are rich in gas and have a relatively young stellar population. Hubble divided them into 2 sub-classes:

Irr I: well-resolved objects showing a population of stars, mainly O and B, but without symmetries or defined arms;

Irr II: chaotic and disturbed galaxies presenting regions extinct by dust.

Over time, Hubble’s work was criticized, especially for its system of cataloging spirals and irregularities. In particular, the French astronomer De Vaucouleurs extended the sequence of spirals by introducing the classes *Sd*, *Sm* and *Im*, in order to replace *Irr I* and introduced the notation *SA* and *SAB*, in which to place, respectively, galaxies completely devoid of bars and galaxies with a weak bar. The scientist also studied the morphological case of the barred galaxies presenting a

Figure 1.2: Hubble-De Vaucouleurs taxonomy of galaxy types. (CC BY-SA 3.0)

ring structure, which he indicated with "r", consequently with "s" he indicated the case of the presence of only the spiral arms and with "rs" the intermediate varieties (see Fig. 1.2).

Nowadays, we know that galaxies, huge self-gravitating systems, can be considered the fundamental building blocks of the Universe. They are mainly made up of stars and star clusters interspersed with immense regions of very low density gas and dust, making up the *ISM*, the *Interstellar Medium*. They are arranged in the Universe forming different structures: from associations, made up of a small number of objects, to clusters and superclusters that contain thousands of them. The space between them, called the *Intergalactic Medium*, is composed of gases with even lower densities, about one atom per cubic meter.

Galaxies can have extremely varied shapes and sizes, and have very different physical characteristics from each other. Nevertheless, the new generation observational tools have allowed the collection and cataloging of a sufficient number of galaxies, making astrophysicists able to treat the phenomenon in a statistical way and therefore to recognize and highlight its main aspects. It is generally observed that:

- the sizes of galaxies are not random, but on average they contain between 10^7 and 10^{12} stars;
- galaxies do not have a sharp boundary, but their radius can be approximated between 100 pc and 50 kpc;
- the dispersion speed of the stars inside them can be identified between $50 \text{ km} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$ and $400 \text{ km} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$;

The estimation of the photometric properties of galaxies is a technique based on the measurement of the flux or intensity of the radiation of a light source, in order to obtain quantitative information on the size, temperature (therefore color) and other physical properties of the extended source. In particular, the surface brightness (or luminosity) is extremely important, being a photometric quantity used to construct a brightness profile of extended objects, capable of estimating the distribution of the light emitted.

Kinematics is another important source of information on galaxies, dealing with the motion of bodies regardless of the causes that generate it. When observing an object in the Universe, an overall speed is obtained, given by the sum of the transverse component with respect to the radius from the Sun (or the Earth), called proper motion, as well as an approaching or moving away component, then directed along the joining, called radial motion. In Astrophysics, to study the kinematics of bodies, one can measure the proper motion by calculating the displacement of the object with respect to the background of the sky, and the radial motion by studying the variations in its emission spectrum. In fact, by exploiting the phenomenon of the Doppler effect (i.e. the movement of wavelengths as a function of the motion of the source with respect to the observer), it is possible to obtain the speed (redshift) at which this occurs. The study of the kinematics of galaxies is generally divided into:

- global kinematics, the study of the motion of a galaxy as a whole;
- internal kinematics, the study of the motion of the stars that make up the galaxy, positioning themselves in its reference system;

The morphological analysis of galaxies plays a central role in understanding the evolution of galaxies and therefore in the possibility of identifying their class. It is, in fact, directly correlated with most of its global physical properties (angular momentum, star formation rate, gas content, etc.). Understanding and reproducing the observed shapes allows us to deepen our knowledge on the mechanisms of formation and evolution. The morphological classification is based on the analysis of the overall shape of a galaxy, that of its components and the integrated spectrum of the object. Obtaining this information is an extremely delicate process as the observation of galactic structures depends on numerous variables such as the exposure time, the spectrum region in which the image is taken or the redshift at which one is observing. Furthermore, the classification criteria chosen are always related to the subjective interpretation of the observer. Therefore, although the morphological classification schemes adopted are valid and of fundamental importance, it is good not to consider them an absolute reality.

We now know that several structural components (bulges, discs, spiral arms and bars) were formed by the aggregation of galaxies (*Combes & Sanders 1981*^[26]; *Elmegreen et al. 1996*^[33]). The analysis of these events highlighted a correlation between the morphology and other properties, also dependent on the history of galaxy formation, such as color, stellar mass and the recent *Star Formation Rate* (*SFR*) (*Baldry et al. 2004*^[5]; *Noeske et al. 2007*^[54]; *Cano-Díaz et al. 2019*^[18]). For example, observing the relationship between mass and *SFR* (*Schiminovich et al. 2007*^[71]; *Goncalves et al. 2012*^[38]; *Peterken et al. 2021*^[60]), it was possible to distinguish between three different populations. Most star-forming galaxies belong to the main sequence and exhibit morphological characteristics typical of spiral or irregular galaxies (also referred to as late-type or *LTG* galaxies). On the other hand, early-type (*ETG*) or first type galaxies are characterized by a much lower *SFR* and different shapes, generally elliptical or dominated by swelling. Finally, there is a transition category between *ETG* and *LTG*, in which the main sequence is attenuated by an intermediate and less densely populated region, called the “green valley” (*Salim 2014*^[69]; *Schawinski et al. 2014*^[70]).

From a more recent historical point of view, galaxies have been visually classified as either early or late-type. There have been several citizen science projects such as the Galaxy Zoo (*Lintott et al. 2008*^[50]; *Nair & Abraham 2010*^[53]; *Simmons et al. 2017*^[76]; *Lingard et al. 2020*^[49]). The common aspect of these projects was of course the huge network of volunteers willing to classify galaxies by visual inspection. Conversely, the analytical methods for the classification of structural properties of galaxies involve modeling the light profiles of the galaxy with 2D analytical functions and their adaptation to galaxy images. The most commonly used model is the Sérsic profile (*Sérsic 1963*)^[74], a function whose parameters describe various structural properties (size, magnitude, ellipticity, inclination and speed) and that describe how the intensity $I(R)$ of light decreases with the radial distance R from the galaxy center (eq. 1.1).

$$I(R) = I_e \exp \left\{ -b_n \left[\left(\frac{R}{R_e} \right)^{1/n} - 1 \right] \right\} \quad (1.1)$$

The index n (called *Sérsic index*), in particular, is able to size the concentration of light, becoming the basic criterion to distinguish between the *ETG* and *LTG* classes. In general, for observations from Earth, the Sérsic model is convolved with the *Point Spread Function* (*PSF*), to take into account the atmospheric seeing and any instrumental systematics of the image. There are also non-parametric methods that can be used to analyze the distribution of light and quantify the concentration of galaxies and the level of asymmetry (*Conselice et al. 2000*)^[27]. In these approaches, *PSF* is not taken into account. Several large catalogs of

galaxy morphologies, based on parametric adaptation (*Simard et al. 2011*)^[75], a non-parametric approach (*Cano-Díaz et al. 2019*)^[18] or both (*Tarsitano et al. 2018*)^[81], are now publicly available for community.

More recently, unlike the aforementioned traditional methods, machine learning algorithms, based on machine learning paradigms, represent an alternative and equally effective way to classify galaxy images. Several experiments, as in (*Banerji et al. 2010*)^[8], (*Dieleman et al. 2015*)^[31] and (*Walmsley et al. 2019*)^[87], highlighted the extreme utility of combining expert visual inspection with artificial intelligence, relying on the use of information acquired in the Galaxy Zoo to train self-adaptive models. The Deep Learning paradigm, in particular supervised convolutional networks (*CNNs*), have been used on *CANDELS* images (*Grogin et al. 2011*)^[43]; *Koekemoer et al. 2011*)^[47], to provide, directly through the images, the classification of galaxies (*Huertas -Company et al. 2015*)^[45]; *Tuccillo et al. 2018*)^[85], to find specific structural parameters such as bars (*Abraham et al. 2018*)^[1], as well as to classify galaxies based on their bulge + disk composition (*Ghosh et al. 2020*)^[37]. Unsupervised methods (*Cheng et al. 2020*)^[24] have also been explored on *SDSS* images (*York et al. 2000*)^[93], revealing the need for data with higher resolution and greater depth, prerogatives envisaged by projects such as Dark Energy Survey (*DES*) (*Dark Energy Survey Collaboration et al. 2016*)^[25] and the *Euclid* space telescope (*Amiaux et al. 2012*)^[4]. Similarly to other areas of astrophysics research, the recent increase in the use of machine learning methods has proved extremely beneficial in understanding the evolutionary paths of galaxies from their morphologies. The main advantage of using these techniques is the ability to emulate the human ability to classify galaxies from ever-exponentially growing volumes of data. Of course, like traditional methods, machine learning techniques also have limitations, particularly with low resolution images, which are partly attributable to high computational costs. More recently, a work has been published that exploits smart methods very efficiently (*Tarsitano et al. 2021*)^[82]. The proposed solution involves an isophotal analysis of the galaxy's light distribution, storing the information in a more manageable data format and performing the classification reducing the total computational costs. It performs first an analysis of main features of the two-dimensional light distribution in an image of a galaxy with isophotal fitting. This then allows it to be revealed in a one-dimensional sequence. The advantage of such an approach is the low complexity of one-dimensional data, which makes both storing and processing data easier and faster than classification methods that directly analyze images (e.g. parametric fitting).

1.2 Aim of this work

To understand why a robust classification of galaxies is so important, let's frame it in the modern scientific context: most of what we know about the universe has been learned within the last 100 years. In broad-brush strokes, we have discovered that our Sun belongs to a huge disk-like conglomeration of about three hundred billion stars, known as the Milky Way galaxy, and the Milky Way itself is only one out of hundreds of billions of galaxies that come in a variety of forms and shapes: the two main types of galaxies are spirals (like our Milky Way) and elliptical galaxies but besides these, there are additional classes such as irregular and dwarf galaxies, active galaxies, and starburst galaxies. These classes differ not only in their morphology, but also in their physical properties such as color (indicating a different stellar content), internal reddening (depending on their dust content), amount of interstellar gas, star-formation rate, etc. Furthermore, in 1929 Edwin Hubble showed that these distant galaxies are not just suspended at rest throughout space, instead they are rushing away from us, and each other, at very high speeds as the entire universe expands. Despite this global expansion, locally, galaxies have been observed to form clusters containing hundreds to thousands of objects.

In 1937, Fritz Zwicky^[94] measured the radial velocities of the galaxies in the Coma Cluster and found that their distribution around the mean has a dispersion much higher than what it was expected considering the estimated mass of the galaxies. This gave birth to the idea that most of the mass of the cluster did not emit light in the visible part of the spectrum. This hypothesis had a strong confirmation a few years later, in 1970, by Vera Rubin and Kent Ford^[67]. They measured the rotation velocity of HI gas clouds in the outer regions of the spiral galaxy M31 and found that additional mass in the outer part of the disk was needed to match the observation with Newton's law of universal gravitation. The nature of the "Dark Matter" that is behind these observational evidences, and how it influences the formation and evolution of galaxies, constitute one of the biggest open questions of modern astrophysics. In the 1980s and 90s radio and optical astronomy flourished with computerized galaxy surveys and instruments, and a detailed map of the distribution of galaxies in space has been compiled, showing that these objects are not distributed randomly in space, on the contrary they are organized in very large-scale structures of filaments and voids. But how did such structures form and evolve? Finally, at the dawn of the 21st century, Riess^[64] and Perlmutter^{[58][58][59]} find observational evidence that the universe is expanding faster than in the past, but what is the mysterious "Dark Energy" that is driving the acceleration of the cosmic expansion?

To answer all these questions, a view of the history of galaxies would be useful but unfortunately, this is physically impossible. However, due to the finite speed of light, we see objects at large distances in an earlier state, as they were in the past. One can now try to identify these distant galaxies and analyse them as progenitors of the various types of galaxies we see in our local universe, reconstructing in this way the main aspects of their history and unfolding the cosmic evolution.

The main objective of this work is therefore to explore the possibility of finding a data-driven solution to the problem of classification of galaxies using the paradigm of the unsupervised machine learning. In particular I want to test two methods that have been shown to produce very interesting results when applied to astronomical data, namely an unsupervised version of a *Random Forest* classifier and a combination of a *T-Distributed Stochastic Neighbor Embedding* dimensionality reduction method and a *Density-Based Spatial Clustering of Applications with Noise* clustering algorithm. To reach this goal I want to prove that is possible, using these methods, to obtain a classification system that is able to identify different classes of galaxies and group them together according to their physical properties.

As a secondary objective I want to test the ability of these methods to detect the presence of any peculiar object in the dataset, the so called ‘unknown unknowns’, which are the most intriguing objects to study as they often show singular physical properties.

In this context I used data coming from the third *Data Release (DR3)* of the *Galaxy And Mass Assembly (GAMA)* survey^[7]. This data release, in fact, provides not only a good quality set of spectra for more than 230,000 objects, but it also provides information about their photometry and other physical properties that are ideal to check the validity and the goodness of a classification system.

Chapter 2

Data

The *GAMA* survey is one of the largest contemporary spectroscopic surveys of low redshift galaxies. In particular, its last data release (*Data Release 3* or *DR3*) provides both photometric and spectroscopic data of more than 230,000 objects along with a precise estimation for their redshift and other physical properties^[7]. It also various visual morphological classifications performed for various samples of *GAMA II* galaxies in the equatorial survey regions:

A first classification was performed by (*Driver et al. 2012*)^[32] and used the following classes: Elliptical, Little Blue Spheroid (*LBS*), Not Elliptical, Star, Artifact and Uncertain. This classification process was executed using $30 \text{ kpc} \times 30 \text{ kpc}$ postage stamps, with a maximum size of 100×100 pixels, generated from the *g*, *i* and *H* band images from the *SDSS*, *VISTA* or *UKIRT Infrared Deep Sky Survey*.

A second classification was performed by (*Kelvin et al. 2014*)^[46] using a classification tree. The first level divides the sample by type (Early Type, Late Type, *LBS*, Star or Artifact), the second by component (Single or Multi) and the third according to whether the object contains or does not contain a bar. For each galaxy the result was then translated to a Hubble type: E, S0-Sa, SB0-SBa, Sab-Scd, SBab-SBcd and Sd-Irr, while retaining the *LBS*, Star and Artifact classifications. The classifications were done independently by three classifier pairs and the final classifications were then compared. If all three classifications for a given galaxy were different, then the classification of one chosen pair was used, otherwise the majority opinion was adopted. The classification was performed on postage stamps that were generated in the exact same way as described above.

A third classification was made by 24 *GAMA* team members who volunteered to classify the merger state of galaxies in the sample described in (*Robotham et al. 2014*)^[66]. Classification weights were determined by comparing the variation in votes amongst different classifiers, with the aim of making the final galaxy classifi-

cation as comparable as possible. The classification was performed using inverted *grK* postage stamps of size $60 \text{ kpc} \times 60 \text{ kpc}$ generated from *SDSS* and *VISTA* data. Classifiers were asked to only consider the disturbed state of the galaxy in the centre of the image as the eventual merger partner was not always visible due to the fixed size of the postage stamps.

The objects that were visually classified, however, constitute a set too small to be efficiently used in conjunction with with the other data provided in the *Data Release*, so the visual morphology classification has not been used. In the following section, I'm going to describe the various data I used, also to provide a robust background, that is needed to better understand the data analysis procedures that will be described in the next chapters.

2.1 Spectroscopic Data and redshift estimation

The main source of spectroscopic data for the *GAMA* survey is the *2dF/AAOmega* multi-fibre instrument on the 3.9m *Anglo-Australian Telescope (AAT)*^[77]. Observations for *GAMA* extended over seven years (referred as *Y1* to *Y7*) and the spectra acquired were all reduced and analysed by the observing team at the telescope in order to estimate the redshift of each object, however the tools and the procedure changed after *Y4*^[51], leading thus to a partial revision of the previously acquired spectra.

2.1.1 Initial redshifting

The ‘*redshifting*’ procedure of the data taken between *Y1* and *Y4* was performed by designated redshifters selected among the observing team. Each redshifter uses the program *runz*^[68] that attempts to identify a redshift of an object by first cross-correlating it with a range of template spectra (including spectra of star-forming, quiescent galaxies, QSOs and A, K and M stars and/or by fitting Gaussians to emission lines (after having interpolated over strong sky lines) and searching for lines matches. After *runz* finds a suitable redshift estimation, the redshifter explicitly assigns to it a quality flag *Q* in the range 0 - 4, where a value lesser than 3 indicates a probably incorrect redshift estimation while the value 3 and 4 indicate respectively a probably and certainly correct redshift estimation.

2.1.2 Re-redshifting

In order to switch to an automated data reduction pipeline, a new redshifting tool, called *autoz*^[6], has been adopted by the observing team and all the spectra

Figure 2.1: Distribution of the **GAMA DR3** objects in terms of the probability **PROB** of the redshift estimated by the program *autoz* being correct.

acquired after Y_4 and the previous spectra with a quality flag $Q \leq 3$ and a small fraction (less than 5%) of the spectra with $Q = 4$ have been ‘*re-redshifted*’. For each input spectrum, the new pipeline first removes the high frequency noise by applying a low-pass filter^[6] then perform a cross-correlation^{[55][13]} with several star and galaxy spectral templates and searches for the one that best matches the input data.

The star spectral templates are obtained from the *Sloan Digital Sky Survey (SDSS) Data Release 5*^{[2][3]} for a total of twenty templates, while a total of eight galaxy spectral templates were generated from the *eigenspectra* derived by (*Bolton et al. 2007*)^[12], six of which correspond as closely as possible to the SDSS DR5 galaxy templates^[78]; one was matched to a post-starburst galaxy template provided by (*V. Wild et al. 2007*)^[88], and one was chosen to fill a gap. Unfortunately, even if for each spectrum the unique identifier of the best matching template is reported, it is stated nowhere which id corresponds to a specific template.

autoz finally assigns a redshift estimation quality flag **PROB** that indicates the probability of the redshift being correct, where a value of 0 indicates that the redshift estimation is certainly wrong and a value of 1 instead indicates that the redshift estimation is certainly true. In order to be consistent with the previous quality flag provided by *runz* and to associate a coherent probability of the correctness of the redshift estimation also for the object that were not ‘*re-redshifted*’, a value of **PROB** ≥ 0.98 has been associated to the object for which $Q = 4$. It is also suggested that only objects with **PROB** ≥ 0.90 should be used in scientific analyses. In Figure 2.1 the distribution of the objects in terms of **PROB** is shown.

After the redshifting procedure, each spectra is saved in a FITS file^[57] as an image containing five rows of 4952 pixels:

- The first row of pixels contains the reduced and calibrated flux density data in $10^{-17} \text{ erg} \cdot \text{s}^{-1} \cdot \text{cm}^{-2} \cdot \text{\AA}^{-1}$ units
- The second row contains the 1σ error for the calibrated spectrum
- The third row contains uncalibrated flux density
- The fourth row contains the 1σ error for the uncalibrated flux density
- The fifth row contains the uncalibrated Sky spectrum used during the data reduction procedure

In the header of each FITS file, besides the value of the estimated redshift, the mapping between each pixel and the corresponding wavelength, as measured in the observer local reference frame, is saved in the form of *World Coordinate System* (*WCS*)^{[42][41]} information.

2.2 Photometric data

The *GAMA DR3* provides also accurate fluxes and uncertainties in 21 photometric bands that extend from the far infrared to the far *UV*. Fluxes are measured using the *Lambda Adaptive Multi-Band Deblending Algorithm in R*^[90] program on multi-band images acquired by five different observatories^[89]:

- Far IR (*FIR*) images are provided by the *Herschel* space observatory^[61]
- Mid IR (*MIR*) imaging is from the *Wide-Field Infrared Survey Explorer* (*WISE*)^[91]
- Near IR (*NIR*) imaging comes from the *Visible and Infrared Telescope for Astronomy* (*VISTA*)^[80] and provides images in the bands *z*, *y*, *j*, *h* and *k*
- The *SDSS* provides optical images in the bands *u*, *g*, *z*, *r* and *i*
- Imaging in the Far and Near UV domain is from *The GALaxy Evolution eXplorer* (*GALEX*)^[52]

The fluxes in the FUV - K bands are also corrected for Galactic extinction using extinction.

2.3 Stellar population and ISM data

The *Data Release 3* of the GAMA survey also contains an estimation of physical stellar population and *interstellar medium* (*ISM*) derived using the program *MAGPHYS*^[30]. This program uses a set of *UV/optical/NIR* spectral templates of stellar populations and *MIR/FIR* templates of dust emission generated using the models published by (*Bruzual & Charlot 2003*)^[16] and (*Charlot & Fall*)^[23] respectively.

For each galaxy, the program compares the *LAMBDA*R photometry of the object in the UV-NIR domain to find the stellar templates that matches the observation. The same procedure is repeated using the photometry in the MIR-FIR bands in order to find the *ISM* templates which are consistent with the observations. Then, these star and dust templates are selected in pairs so that the energy lost from the stellar emission due to dust attenuation is balanced by energy emitted by the dust. Finally the overall best fitting pair is chosen and the parameters of the models used to generate the two templates are stored in a catalog.

2.4 Emission and absorption lines measurement

For each of the spectra having a value of the a redshift estimation quality $\text{PROB} \geq 0.4$ and a value of the redshift in the range $0.002 \leq z \leq 1.35$, three tables are provided in which there are line flux and equivalent width of various emission and absorption lines^[39].

- The first table contains line measurements derived from single-Gaussian fits to twelve important emission lines in five different spectral regions:
 - 3626 – 3779Å for the lines of OIIB and OIIR
 - 4711 – 5157Å for the lines of H β , OIIIIB and OIIIR
 - 6270 – 6394Å for the lines of OIB and OIR
 - 6398 – 6710Å for the lines of NIIB, H α and NIIR
 - 6616 – 6831Å for the lines of SIIB and SIIR

as well as the parameter D4000 that measures the strength of the break at 4000Å measured using the method of (*Gorgas et al. 1998*)^[40]. The value of this parameter is the ratio of the average flux densities in the spectral regions 4000–4100Å and 3850–3950Å^[36].

- The second table contains more complex two component Gaussian fits to the *Ha* and β lines

- The third table contains equivalent widths^[21] of 51 absorption and emission lines species, measured using the techniques outlined by (*Cardiel et al. 1998*)^[19]

2.5 Stellar masses

Stellar masses and other ancillary stellar population parameters have been derived through stellar population synthesis modeling of broadband photometry for all galaxies with a value of the redshift estimation quality `PROB` ≥ 0.4 and a value of the redshift in the range $0 \leq z \leq 0.65$. The model fitting procedure is done using the stellar evolution models of (*Bruzual & Charlot 2003*)^[16] assuming a Chabrier stellar *Initial Mass Function (IMF)* described in (*Chabrier et al. 2003*)^[22] and a Calzetti dust curve (*Calzetti et al. 2000*)^[17]. The stellar population synthesis models are defined by four parameter, which are^[83]:

- The e-folding time for the exponentially decay *Star Formation History (SFH)*
- The time since formation
- The stellar metallicity
- The dust attenuation

Because the *LAMBDA*R photometry does not purports to necessarily represent the total flux in any particular band, an aperture correction is required for integrated quantities like stellar mass, luminosity, etc. The parameter `fluxscale` is provided for this purpose and the user of the catalog is trusted to apply the following correction:

- The recommended total mass should be computed as

$$\log_{10}(M_{total}^*) = \text{logmstar} + \log_{10}(\text{fluxscale}) - 2 \times \log_{10}\left(\frac{h}{0.7}\right) \quad (2.1)$$

- The recommended absolute magnitude in the *X*-band

$$M_X = \text{absmag}_X - 2.5 \times \log_{10}(\text{fluxscale}) + 5 \times \log_{10}\left(\frac{h}{0.7}\right) \quad (2.2)$$

Where the parameters `logmstar` and `absmag_X` are respectively the base 10 logarithm of the mass of luminous material time of observation and the absolute magnitude in the band *X* as resulted from the stellar population synthesis model

fitting, while h is the dimensionless Hubble constant. When apply this correction one has also to check that the value of the parameter `fluxscale` makes sense (i.e. is greater than or equal to unity) and that the order of magnitude of the correction is not greater that the order of magnitude of the uncorrected value. These correction are also source of uncertainty that is not quantified in the catalog, which therefore should be considered as a lower limit.

Chapter 3

Methodologies

The unsupervised learning paradigm includes a wide set of statistical tools used in data exploration, such as clustering analysis, dimensionality reduction, visualization, and outlier detection. Such tools are particularly significant in scientific research, being potential means of new discoveries or of extracting new knowledge from data. Moreover, we know that, in particular, visual inspection is impractical in modern astronomical surveys, characterized by hundreds or thousands of features per each of its billion objects. For this reason, it is necessary to take advantage of statistical tools for this task. Unsupervised learning methods take only measured features as input, with unknown labels. Their output is typically a non-linear and non-invertible transformation of the input dataset, associating different objects to different clusters, or a smaller representation of the objects in the sample, or even a list of peculiar objects.

However, these algorithms often have several external free hyper-parameters, which cannot be optimized via the cost function of the algorithm. Different choices of these parameter can result in significantly different results, leading to different interpretations of the same dataset. The output of an unsupervised learning algorithm must be interpreted with extreme caution, taking into account its internal choices and cost function, and the sensitivity of the output to changes in its hyper-parameters. However, since unsupervised learning is typically used for data exploration, they can be used without a precisely predetermined goal. The lack of a precise goal is often not critical and it just makes more difficult to find convergence to the optimal solution.

Figure 3.1: The image show the process to generate a synthetic dataset from a given data distribution, taken from (Baron & Poznanski 2017)^[9]. In the left panel the original distribution of data is plotted along with the marginal distribution for each feature, shown in on the top and left side of the plot. In the right panel, instead, there is the distribution of the synthetic data obtained by the original one, by removing the covariance between the features.

3.1 Unsupervised Random Forest

In *Machine Learning* theory, the so-called ensemble models are methods characterized by the combination of different supervised learning techniques, resulting in a single predictive model, capable of improving overall performance, compared to single supervised algorithms. They also combine information obtained from learning performed on different subsets of the training set. One of the most popular methods is Random Forest, a collection of Decision Trees (Breiman *et al.* 1984^[15]; Breiman 2001^[14]). Recall that a decision tree is a non-parametric model built during the training phase, formed by a tree chart from top to bottom and used in both classification and regression problems.

In the astrophysics field, the Random Forest model has often been used and validated in various contexts in supervised mode (for example, Carliles *et al.* 2010^[20]; Bloom *et al.* 2012^[11]; Yong *et al.* 2018^[92]), but, more recently, it has proved to be also valid in unsupervised environments, for example to determine similarity measures between samples of the same dataset (Baron & Poznanski 2017^[9]; Reis *et al.* 2018a,b^[62]).

In such context, the *Unsupervised Random Forest (URF)* is a peculiar model, which is able to handle unsupervised problems by converting them to supervised cases. In an unsupervised scenario, the dataset consists only of measured features,

without labels, in the form of an $N \times M$ matrix, with N objects and M features. The process of converting an unsupervised learning problem into a supervised one, that can be handled by the standard *Random Forest* model, consists in the construction of a synthetic dataset. This dataset is again an $N \times M$ matrix but where each feature is obtained by sampling from the marginal distribution of the same feature present in the original dataset. This process is illustrated in Figure (Fig. 3.1) with an example from (*Baron & Poznanski 2017*^[9]), where the objects in the dataset have only two features. In the left panel the original dataset is shown along with the marginal distributions of each feature, while the right panel shows the synthetic dataset and the marginal distributions. From this example it's easy to see that the features of the objects in the synthetic dataset show the same marginal distribution as the ones in the original dataset, but are deprived of the calculated covariance.

The synthetic and the original dataset are then merged, labeling each object depending on whether it belongs to the original dataset or to the synthetic one, and the standard *Random Forest* model is then trained to distinguish between the two classes. In fact, in the training phase, the *Random Forest* learns to detect the presence of covariance between data, which is present only in the original dataset and not in the synthetic one. Consequently, the most important features in decision trees will be those that have correlations with others. At the end of the learning process, the distance between the different objects (in the original dataset) is defined as follows: each pair of objects is propagated through all decision trees in the forest and their similarity index $S_{i,j}$ is defined as the number of times they have both been classified as a real object and reached the same terminal leaf. Since this similarity index can range from 0 to the number N of trees in our forest, the distance between any two objects is defined as $D_{i,j} = 1 - S_{i,j}/N$. S measures the similarity between any two objects in the dataset, since if two objects follow a similar path within the decision tree (and thus end in similar leaves) then this means that they have similar features, and consequently are represented by the same model (see *Baron & Poznanski 2017*^[9]). Another index that measures the distance between the objects in the space of the feature, is the *weirdness* index, which is defined as $w_i = \sum_j D_{i,j}/N$ and ranges from 0 to 1. This index represent the average distance of an object from all the others in the dataset, meaning that an object with a high value of w is probably an object that has peculiar physical properties.

(*Reis et al. 2018a,b*)^{[62][63]} showed that this definition of similarity provides valuable information about different physical properties of the objects in a dataset. In particular, this method was applied to the infrared spectra of stars and they

showed that this metric tracks the physical properties of stars, such as metallicity, temperature and surface gravity. The metric works well for spectra and plots information from different emission and absorption lines and their connection with continuous emission^{[62][63]}.

3.2 T-Distributed Stochastic Neighbor Embedding

Dealing high dimensional data is an important problem when one wants to find correlations among the physical properties of astronomical objects. *Machine Learning* offers several tools that are able to project high dimensional data in onto a lower dimensional space (called *embedded space* or *embedding*), of typically 2 or 3 dimensions, and thus generating a more or less faithful representation of the data distribution in the original space. Dimensionality reduction is not only useful to visualize data distribution in the space of their features, but in many cases is a mandatory step to perform before proceeding in the data analysis. This is particularly true when dealing with unsupervised machine learning clustering algorithms. Due to the “curse of dimensionality”, a term coined by Richard E. Bellman^[10], when the number of dimensions increases, the volume of the feature space increases so fast that objects become sparser and sparser. This problem represents a serious obstacle for all the algorithms that rely on detecting differences in the density of the data, like for example many clustering methods.

A dimensionality reduction method that has rapidly become widespread in the *Machine Learning* field is the so called *T-Distributed Stochastic Neighbor Embedding* (*T-SNE*), introduced by (*Van der Maaten & Hinton 2008*)^[86]. The biggest advantage of this model is that it can be used on datasets having several a several thousands of features while still generating a meaningful 2D embedding. Moreover, each object in the original high dimensional space is mapped exactly to one single point in the embedded space, this characteristic makes *T-SNE* much more precise compared to other models, like the *Self Organizin Map* (*Kohonen 1997*)^[48], that map sub-regions of the original feature space into sub-regions of the embedded space. On the other hand, however, *T-SNE* has the disadvantage that is unable to map any new data added to the dataset requiring a whole new training process.

Given a set of objects $\{\bar{x}_1, \dots, \bar{x}_N\}$ in the high dimensional feature space and the corresponding set of objects $\{\bar{y}_1, \dots, \bar{y}_N\}$ in the embedded space, *T-SNE* computes two probabilities p_{ij} and q_{ij} that are directly proportional to the similarity of the objects \bar{x}_i, \bar{x}_j and \bar{y}_i, \bar{y}_j respectively (and thus inversely proportional the their

distance). Then it computes the *Kullback-Leibler* (*K-L*) divergence cost function, defined by the equation (eq. 3.1) and minimizes it using the gradient-descent method.

$$D_{K-L}(p_{ij}, q_{ij}) = \sum_{i \neq j} p_{ij} \log \frac{p_{ij}}{q_{ij}} \quad (3.1)$$

The way the probability p_{ij} is computed depends also on two main parameters:

- The metric used to compute the distance between two points
- The value of the **perplexity**, which indirectly regulates how far two points must be from each other to be considered dissimilar.

The use of the *K-L* divergence implies high penalties for configurations where two points that are similar in the original space are placed far from each other in the embedded space. The minimization process then generates a low dimensionality embedding that preserves the similarity of the objects in the original feature space.

3.3 Density-Based Spatial Clustering of Applications with Noise

From a point of view of the unsupervised paradigm of machine learning, clustering algorithms play a fundamental role in identifying classes in spatial datasets. However, the effective use of these methods cannot be separated from three requirements:

- 1) A minimum knowledge of the domain to determine the input parameters;
- 2) Discovery of clusters with arbitrary shape
- 3) Good efficiency on large databases

The most well-known clustering algorithms often do not offer a solution that contemplates the combination of these requirements.

In the 1996 (*Ester et al.*)^[34] proposed a new method, called *Density-Based Spatial Clustering of Applications with Noise* (*DBSCAN*), introducing a density-based notion of clusters designed to discover clusters of arbitrary shape. The method requires only an input parameter and assists the user in determining an appropriate value for it. When observing the sample sets of points depicted in figure (Fig. 3.2), we can easily detect clusters of points and noise points that do not belong to any of these clusters, this is because within each cluster there

Figure 3.2: Examples of cluster shapes (courtesy from Ester et al. 1996)^[34]

is a typical density of points, considerably higher than outside of the cluster. Furthermore, the density within the areas of noise is lower than the density in any of the clusters.

To find a cluster, DBSCAN starts with an arbitrary point p and finds all points density-reachable from p . There are two parameters that controls whether a point is density-reachable:

- **eps**: the maximum distance between two points to be considered neighbours;
- **min_samples**: the number of neighbours a point must have to be considered part of a cluster (core point);

If p is a core point, then all the density-reachable point are found, yielding to a cluster, otherwise p is classified as a noise point and the algorithm check the next point in the dataset. The procedure ends when all points are maker as noise or as member of a cluster. However, since we use global values for **eps** and **min_samples**, *DBSCAN* may merge two clusters into a single one. If two clusters of different density are close to each other. Let the distance between two sets of points S_1 and S_2 be defined as $d(S_1, S_2) = \min\{d(p, q) \mid p \in S_1, q \in S_2\}$. Then, two clusters will be separated from each other only if the distance between them is larger than **eps**. Consequently, a recursive call of DBSCAN may be necessary for the detected clusters with a higher value of **min_samples**.

(Ester et al. 1996)^[34] proposed also an heuristic to find the proper couple of parameters **eps** and **min_samples** for the lesser dense cluster in the dataset, based on the following observation: given a point p that belongs to a cluster Ω , let's denote with d_n the distance of p from its n -th nearest neighbour, then in the circle of radius d_n and centrer p there are exactly $n+1$ points (this is not true only if there

Figure 3.3: Examples of a k -dist graph.

is more than one neighbour at the same distance from p , but usually it's unlikely). Since points in a cluster are more or less uniformly distributed (i.e. they are not in straight lines), a variation of n does not imply a big variation of the distance d_n . Then, if we define a function $f_n : \Omega \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ so that $f_n(p) = d_n \forall p \in \Omega$ and sort the points in an ascending order of d_n we obtain a so called k -dist graph (Fig. 3.3), that can give some hints about the density distribution in the dataset. Now, if we chose a point p^* and set the value of the `eps` to $d_n^* = d_n(p^*)$ and the value of `min_samples` to n , then all the points for which $d_n \leq d_n^*$ will be members of a cluster. Because points that are in cluster have a value of d_n lower respect to the one that are isolated, the value of `eps` and `min_samples` can be deduced by the change of the steepness of the k -dist graph. However, in practical terms, at the end, the method *DBSCAN* requires only the `Eps` parameter choice (*Schubert et al. 2017*)^[72].

Chapter 4

Data preparation and analysis

4.1 Spectra selection and reduction

In order to minimize the influence of the noise on the final classification procedure, I selected a sample of good quality spectra from the original catalog of 166,322 objects. A good estimator of the quality of the spectrum is the probability `PROB` that has been provided by *autoz*: in fact, as said in **Section 2.1.2**, only those objects having a value of $PROB \geq 0.9$ should be used for scientific purposes. To be more restrictive, I used the median value of `PROB`=0.9997 as a threshold, leading to a sample of approximately 83,000 spectra. Unfortunately, not all the FITS files containing the actual spectral data were available, resulting in a final sample of 72,283 spectra.

Due to the *Cosmological Redshift*^{[21][35]}, the same spectral feature will be observed at different wavelengths in the observer local reference frame, depending on the redshift value. For this reason, in order to have a homogeneous dataset, using the python package `specutils`^[79] all the spectra have been brought to rest-frame by correcting for the effect of the redshift using the formula 4.1.

$$\lambda = \frac{\lambda_{obs}}{1 + z} \quad (4.1)$$

Where z is the value of the redshift, λ_{obs} is the wavelength in the observer local reference frame and λ is the corresponding wavelength in the object rest frame. Then for each spectrum the continuum has been estimated using the `specutil` function `fit_generic_continuum` that smooths the spectrum with a running median filter and the fits it with a *Chebyshev series*^[65] of the first kind and third

degree, whose general expression is given by equation 4.2.

$$P(x) = \sum_{i=0}^{i=3} C_i \cdot T_i(x) \quad (4.2)$$

where $T_i(x)$ is the *Chebyshev polynomial* of first kind and degree i and C_i are the coefficients found during the fitting procedure. Finally each spectrum has been normalized by dividing it by the corresponding fitted continuum (Fig. 4.1).

The normalized spectrum then has been re-binned and trimmed using the `LinearInterpolatedResampler` function of `specutils` to get a total of 2,250 spectral features in the range $3700 - 7000\text{\AA}$, this range has been chosen to minimize the number of missing data while retaining the majority of emission and absorption lines and the break at 4000\AA .

Finally, to fill any missing data still present, the sample of spectra has been imputed using the python package `scikit-learn`^[56] (Figura 4.2). The imputation process consists of two phases: firstly, for each wavelength bin the median value of the normalized flux density is computed considering all the spectra, then any missing data is replaced with the corresponding median value. The imputed dataset S_i has been passed then to *URF* and *T-SNE* for the analysis process.

4.2 Analysis with *URF*

As the first step, I built a synthetic dataset of spectra of the same size as the original S_i , as described in the previous section, but with values of the normalized flux density draw randomly from the same marginal distribution of each wavelength bin (Fig. 4.3). I then merged the two datasets, labeling each object according to whether it was a real one or a synthetic one, and used them to train a *URF* model built with the python package `scikit-learn` and containing 6000 trees.

With the trained *URF* model I then computed the *weirdness* index w according to the procedure described in Section 3.1. The distribution of the objects relative to this indicator is substantially uniform except for a small peak that corresponds to objects having a very high value of weirdness, centred around $w = 0.99$ (Fig. 4.4): these could be very peculiar objects that may be worthy of further investigation. Therefore I set an arbitrary threshold of $w^* = 0.99$ to select all objects with $w \geq w^*$, obtaining so a subset S_w of 1,837 objects.

To perform a statistical analysis of the physical properties of this objects, I matched the whole dataset of spectra with the catalogs containing the stellar

masses, the absorption and emission line fluxes and the information on the stellar population and ISM content, leading to a subset S_T of 57,390 spectra ($\approx 80\%$ of the initial 72,283 in the input dataset).

For the objects in the subset S_w , I then derived their distribution relative to the total stellar masses (corrected with the prescription given by the formula 2.1), the D4000 parameter, the redshift z , some of the most important lines (namely the lines H_α , H_β , NII, OIII and OI), and the median *Star Formation Rate* in the last 10^6 , 10^7 , 10^8 and 10^9 years. I then compared each of these distributions with the corresponding one generated using the whole sample S_T and performed a *Student's t-Test*^[28] and a *Kolmogorov-Smirnov*^[44] test. This is needed in order to establish quantitatively whether the sample S_w of objects with high value of w is actually a representative sample of S_T or, in other words, if it contains objects drawn randomly from the latter and therefore if the training process of the *URF* model failed.

The figures in appendix A show the comparison between the various pairs of distributions, along with the *p-values* of the *Kolmogorov-Smirnov* test and *Student's t-Tests*. For all the the aforementioned physical properties, with the exception of the parameter D4000, both *Kolmogorov-Smirnov* test and *Student's t-Tests* show that we can reject the hypothesis that S_i is merely a random sub-sample of S_T with a confidence level greater than 95%.

This analysis, however, has shown also that the objects in the sample S_w are not peculiar and does not have any uncommon physical properties: for almost all of them, the value of each physical property listed above is consistent within 3σ with the mean value computed on the whole dataset S_T , as also can be seen in figures.

4.3 Analysis with *T-SNE* and *DBSCAN*

4.3.1 *T-SNE* 2-D embedded spaces generation

Like what I have done in the *URF* experiment, the first step is the preparation of the input dataset for *DBSCAN*. I started by creating several *T-SNE* models using the python package *scikit-learn*^[56], each using a different metric to calculate the distance of the objects in the parameter space of the dataset, that is the dataset of normalized spectra S_i . Because the **perplexity** is the other main parameter that can be tuned to obtain an optimal result, I trained all the different *T-SNE* models using different values of **perplexity**: I started with a value of 5, then used a value of 10 and then incremented the value by 10 up to a value of 80. Each *T-SNE* model was configured to generate a bi-dimensional embedded space.

The four metrics tested are all defined in the *scipy*^[73] python package as following: given two objects of a dataset, their positions in the N -dimensional parameters $\Omega \subseteq \mathbb{R}^N$ being \bar{u} and \bar{v} , and denoting with x_i the i -th component of a vector \bar{x}

- The *Bray-Curtis* distance, defined as

$$d(\bar{u}, \bar{v}) = \frac{\sum_{i=0}^N (v_i - u_i)}{\sum_i (v_i + u_i)} \quad (4.3)$$

- The *Mahalanobis* distance, defined as

$$d(\bar{u}, \bar{v}) = \sqrt{(\bar{u} - \bar{v}) (\sigma^{-1}) (\bar{u} - \bar{v})^T} \quad (4.4)$$

where σ^{-1} is the inverse of the co-variance matrix of the dataset.

- The *Hamming* distance, defined as the proportion of the vector elements between \bar{u} , \bar{v} which are not equal

$$d(\bar{u}, \bar{v}) = \frac{\sum_{i=0}^N \delta_{u_i, v_i}}{N} \quad (4.5)$$

where, with an abuse of notation, $\delta_{a,b} = 1$ if $a = b$ and 0 otherwise $\forall a, b \in \mathbb{R}$.

- The *Correlation* distance, defined as

$$d(\bar{u}, \bar{v}) = 1 - \frac{(\bar{u} - \bar{1}\langle\bar{v}\rangle) \cdot (\bar{v} - \bar{1}\langle\bar{u}\rangle)}{\|\bar{u} - \bar{1}\langle\bar{u}\rangle\|_2 \|\bar{v} - \bar{1}\langle\bar{v}\rangle\|_2} \quad (4.6)$$

where $\langle\bar{x}\rangle$ indicates the mean value of all the component of the vector \bar{x} .

The first experiment with the *Bray-Curtis* distance and an initial perplexity value of 5 took seven days to complete, meaning that approximately other two months were needed to test the remaining eight selected values of *perplexity* and find the optimal value. Similarly, the experiment run using the *Mahalanobis* distance ran for a bit longer time and when it exceeded the 10 days I decided to stop it, since at this point it would have taken at least three months to find an optimal value for the *perplexity* parameter. For this reason I did not proceed further the analysis with these two metrics.

On the other hand, both the experiments executed with the *Hamming* and *Correlation* distances and an initial perplexity value of 5 ended in a reasonable amount of time, giving also valid results. In fact, the objects distribution in the

two generated embedded spaces shows distinct structures, as it can be seen in figures (Fig. 4.5b) and (Fig. 4.5b). Therefore, using these two metrics, I ran the remaining experiments using the other selected values of the *perplexity* parameter. I found that using the *Hamming* distance the best value of *perplexity* to be used is 30, while for the *Correlation* distance it is 80. Since in the latter case the best value found for the *perplexity* parameter was also the highest of the set I tested, I run other two experiment with a *perplexity* value of 100 and 120 obtaining a worst result in both cases.

As sanity check, I plotted the distribution of the objects in the two embedded spaces in function of the redshift (Fig 4.6). In fact, since all information about the redshift has been removed in the dataset preparation, described in the previous section, by de-redshifting the spectra to the object rest-frame, any strong correlation between the data distribution and the redshift would indicate a failure either in the training of the *T-SNE* model or in input dataset preparation. From the distribution of the objects in the embedded space generated with the *Hamming* distance 4.6b, it's evident the presence of several well defined clusters. Moreover, the plot shows that object of the same cluster have a very similar value redshift. For this reason only the embedding generated using the *Correlation* distance (henceforth denoted as E_c), that does not show such anomaly, has been further analysed with *DBSCAN*.

The two embeddings generated with the *Correlation* distances best values of the **perplexity** parameter has been passed to *DBSCAN* to identify and analyse any cluster present.

4.3.2 Analysis of the ‘*Correlation*’ embedding

I created a *DBSCAN* model using the python package *scikit-learn*. The first run on the embedding E_c showed a big central cluster surrounded by a cloud of equally spaced points that are classified as ‘noise’ by the algorithm. I obtained the best separation between the noise and the central cluster using a value of the parameter $\text{eps} = 4$. I then ran *DBSCAN* another time on the central cluster in order to detect the presence of any sub-cluster of objects. I then applied this procedure recursively to each sub-cluster, and automate the whole process with the following prescription:

- fixing the recursion depth to 3, meaning that no more sub-clusters are searched in clusters that already have 3 ancestors.
- defining the maximum number of sub-cluster `max_sub_cluster` that each cluster can contain.

- defining an initial value `initial_eps` of the `eps` parameter.
- defining the `eps_decrease_rate`.
- A *DBSCAN* model is run with a value of the `eps` equal to `initial_eps`. If only one sub-cluster is found in the current cluster, then the `eps` is increased by a factor of $2/3$, else if the number of sub-clusters found is greater than `max_sub_cluster` then the `eps` is reduced by a factor of `eps_decrease_rate`. This process is tried iteratively for a maximum of 10 times.
- If valid sub-clusters are found and the recursion depth has not been reached yet, then the `initial_eps` is set to the value `eps × eps_decrease_rate` and the whole procedure is applied to each sub-cluster

With this procedure I was able to identify a total of 27 distinct clusters of objects (Fig. 4.7). To each cluster I assigned an integer ID from 0 to 26, and assigned -2 to the set of noise points. However, in order to be considered as an actual class every cluster must be a homogeneous set of objects, namely the objects in each cluster must have the same physical properties. To verify this, I performed first a visual inspection of the spectra: for each cluster I randomly selected 200 objects, then for each object I took the corresponding normalized spectra from the initial dataset S_i , finally with these spectra I created an image in which each row of pixels corresponds to a different spectrum, each column of pixels corresponds to a wavelength bin and the brightness of each pixel is directly proportional to the normalized flux density. Looking at these images (in appendix B), it is worth to see that each cluster contains objects having very similar spectral features and, moreover, that spectra of objects belonging to different clusters show different spectral features. To show this in a quantitative way, similarly to what I have done in the section 4.2, I matched the dataset with the catalogs containing the stellar masses, the absorption and emission line fluxes and the information on the stellar population and ISM content, leading to a subset S_T of 57,390 spectra ($\approx 80\%$ of the initial 72,283 in the input dataset). For the objects of each class I then computed the average value and standard error and the relative standard error for different physical properties. As it can be seen from the histograms in appendix C, not only the different clusters show different mean values for some physical property, but they also have relative standard errors lower than 5% for most of them. Interestingly enough we note that also in this case there is a sort of correlation between the different classes and the mean redshift value.

Figure 4.1: An example of a spectrum of a galaxy with the fitted continuum (orange line in the upper panel) and the same spectrum normalized by subtracting the continuum (lower panel).

Figure 4.2: The figure shows a random sample of normalized spectra before (upper panel) and after (lower panel) the imputation process. Each line in the image is a different spectra shown in false color, where yellow represent a higher value of the normalized flux density and blue indicates a lower value, white spaces are missing data.

Figure 4.3: Density distribution of two pair of spectroscopic features (namely, the normalize flux density in the 4800 Å and 5000 Å) belonging to the original sample of spectra (left panel) and to the synthetic dataset generated from the same marginal distributions of the real one, by removing the co-variance among original data (right panel).

Figure 4.4: The histogram in red shows the object distribution according to their weirdness index value, obtained using a *URF* model. In blue are highlighted the 'weirdest' objects with a weirdness value greater than $w^* = 0.99$

Figure 4.5: The visualization of the T -SNE embedding of the dataset S_i , obtained with a value of the perplexity parameter equal to 5, for different metrics: (a) *Bray-Curtis* distance; (b) *Hamming* distance; (c) *Correlation* distance. Each point in the image corresponds to a different object of the dataset. Images are also color-mapped to highlight the local density of points, where a blue color indicates a low local density while a green/yellow color indicates a higher point density

Figure 4.6: The visualization of the T -SNE embedding of the dataset S_i , obtained with the *Hamming* distance and a value of *perplexity* = 30 (a) & (b) and the *Correlation* distance and a value of *perplexity* = 80 (c) & (d). Each point in the image corresponds to a different object of the dataset. Images (a) and (c) are color-mapped to highlight the local density of points, where a blue color indicates a low local density while a green/yellow color indicates a higher point density. Images (b) and (d) are color-mapped in function of the redshift, where a bluer color indicates a low value of the redshift density while a redder color indicates a higher value.

Figure 4.7: The image shows the distribution of the objects in the embedding E_c generated using the T -SNE model with the *Correlation* distance and a value of *perplexity* = 80. The points are color-mapped to highlight different clusters found using *DBSCAN*, where each color indicate a different cluster.

Chapter 5

Discussion of the results

Regarding *URF*, I found that the distribution of the object relative to the *weirdness* index is almost uniform and no information about the presence of a particular class of objects can be extrapolated. I also shown that, even if there was a small set of objects that have a very high weirdness value, they are not peculiar object as their physical properties were within the average on the whole dataset. A possible explanation to this result, which is also the most probable one, is a selection effect. In the preparation of the input sample of good quality spectra S_i , in fact, I choose those objects that had a value of $PROB \geq 0.9997$. This choice on one hand assures that the selected spectra have a high signal to noise ratio and have well defined spectral features, but on the other hand could exclude from the dataset the most peculiar objects. The $PROB$ parameter is, in fact, an estimation on how well the program *autoz* was able to identify the redshift, but the process of the redshift estimation relies on the use of a set of quite standard cross-correlation spectral templates. This means that, very likely, any peculiar object whose spectra did not match with any template have been assigned a relative low value of $PROB$.

Regarding the result obtained using *T-SNE*, first of all, I have to make some considerations about why the clusters found using *Hamming* distance strongly correlated with the redshift. For how the metric is defined, the similarity of two objects depends on the number of features that present the same value. If it is almost impossible that the actual spectral features (i.e. emission and absorption lines) have the exact same value in two different objects, this does not hold for the imputed data. During the imputation procedure, in fact, each missing data is replaced with the median value of the corresponding feature computed on the whole dataset. This imply that objects with a missing data in the same feature are considered very similar. Furthermore, the number of missing data does depend on the redshift: when a spectra is brought to the rest frame and then trimmed to fit it in a specific range of wavelength (Fig. 5.1), that is exactly what I did in section

Figure 5.1: The image illustrate what happens when a spectra (upper panel) is brought to the rest frame and trimmed in a specific range of wavelengths (lower panel). In some circumstances the process can lead to missing data (in black) at the edges of the de-redshifted spectra.

4.1, then missing data can appear at one edge of the spectra simply because there are no data at those wavelength in the original spectra.

Using the *Correlation* distance instead, I found that the each cluster identified contains objects that show very similar spectral feature and have very similar physical properties and thus can be considered fully fledged classes and this fulfills the main goal of this work. This is particularly evident from figure (Fig. 4.7), that shows the distribution of the objects in the embedded space generate by *T-SNE*, where each point has been colored to highlight the cluster it belongs. From this plot it is clear that the cluster identified are well defined and have a regular shape, in contrast to the ones found using the other metric, and this is a very strong indication of the good quality of the result of the classification.

It is worth to see from figure(Fig. C.1c) that the classes of objects distribute in a redshift range that goes from ≈ 0.1 to ≈ 0.4 , with object of each class having a quite similar redshift. This could indicate three things:

- a) The imputed missing data play somehow a minor role in the computation of the similarity of two objects also using the *Correlation* metric, even if in this case I shown that the spectral features are the main driver of the classification.
- b) The presence of other selection effects in the original dataset.
- c) The abundance of the different types of objects changes with the redshift.

Whatever the answer is, the fact that the 27 clusters found group together objects having similar value of the redshift, despite no information about the latter have been passed to the ML models used, is an interesting and remarkable result.

In particular class 9 is very interesting because it contains relatively near galaxies, with a mean redshift of $z \approx 0.1$, that show a median metallicity of ≈ 0.65 , meaning that they contain a population of relatively young stars. They also have a low total star mass of $\approx 10^9 M_{sun}$, that could suggest they could belong to the family of *Dwarf Galaxies*.

Chapter 6

Conclusions

In this work, I investigated the possibility of finding a data-driven solution to the problem of automatic classification of galaxies using unsupervised machine learning methods. For this purpose I extracted a sample of approximately 72,000 good quality spectra of galaxies from the GAMA DR3. Each spectrum has been normalized by fitting and subtracting its continuum, then it has been de-redshifted to the rest frame and, finally, it has been rebinned and trimmed to get a set of fluxes in 2250 different wavelength bins ranging from 3700Å to 7000Å. This range has been chosen to minimize the number of noisy pixels and missing data. The whole sample of spectra has been imputed to fill any missing data.

I first analyzed the sample of spectra using an *Unsupervised* version of a *Random Forest* classifier, from which however no conclusive result emerged. In a second experiment, instead, using a combination of a *T-Distributed Stochastic Neighbor Embedding* dimensionality reduction method and a *Density-Based Spatial Clustering of Applications with Noise* clustering algorithm, I was able to identify 27 cluster of objects. The physical properties of this objects have been compared to confirm that each cluster truly contains similar objects, achieving thus the main goal of this work. I also generated a set of 27 spectral cross-correlation templates, one for each class found.

These results are obviously only a starting point for future works: a first next step should be to analyse the spectral template generated, as they represent the mean normalized spectrum for each class, in order to link the classes found to the current classes of galaxies used in the literature. Another natural prosecution of the work is to use the classes found as knowledge base to train and test other supervised machine learning algorithms, and run the latter on the object that were not in the sub-sample used in this work. Finally, the same procedure could be applied to other sets of spectral data and compare the properties of the classes that will be detected to the ones I found in this work.

Appendices

Appendix A

Statistics for the sample S_w

The figures show the comparisons of the distribution of the objects with $w \geq 0.99$ (in orange) and the one of the objects in the whole dataset (in blue), relative to various physical properties: the corrected total stellar mass `logmstar_total`(a); the spectroscopic redshift z (b); the intensity of the 4000 Å break (c); the fluxes of various lines: H_β (d); NII (b); OIII (e); H_α (g); the mean *Star formation Rate* in the last 10^6 y (h), 10^7 y (i), 10^8 y (j) and 10^9 y (k).

In the panels on the left the cumulative curves are shown along with the *Kolmogorov-Smirnov* distance and *p-value*, while in the panels on the right there are the distributions along with the *p-value* of the *Student's t-Test*; The two x with the error-bars indicate the position of the mean value of the two distributions and their 3σ standard deviation, the black one is referred to S_T and the red one is referred to S_w

Figure A.1

(d)

(e)

(f)

(g)

(h)

(i)

(j)

(k)

Appendix B

Comparison of spectra

The images below are a comparison of the normalized spectra of different objects belonging to the various classes that have been found using *DBSCAN* and *T-SNE* with ‘correlation’ metric. Each image is constructed by randomly drawing a sample of 200 spectra for each class, then these spectra are stacked vertically in such a way that each row of pixels corresponds to a single spectra. The images are color-mapped so that a yellow color corresponds to a higher value of the normalized flux density, while dark blue corresponds to a lower value. It’s easy to see that objects belonging to the same class shows very similar spectral features.

Appendix C

Statistics for the *DBSCAN* classes

The following charts show the average value of various physical properties for each class that has been found using *DBSCAN* on the embedding E_c . In each chart, on the x-axis the ID of each class is shown and the height of each bar indicates the average value of the property of the corresponding class. The error bars indicate the standard error, while on the top part of the chart the relative standard errors are reported.

(e)

(f)

(g)

Appendix D

Spectral template

The following images show the spectral templates of the various classes that have been found using *DBSCAN* and *T-SNE* with ‘correlation’ metric. The template are created by averaging the normalized spectra (obtained in **Section 4.1**) of all the objects belonging to the same class. Fits files containing the template data can be available here [29].

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